

Supplementary Material

Table S1. Primers, Genbank accession numbers and reference articles for sequences of target and housekeeping genes.

Gene *	Primer Sequence 5'-3' (F) and 5'-3' (R)	GenBank Access No.	Reference
<i>lpl</i>	CGT TGC CAA GTT TGT GAC CTG AGG GTG TTC TGG TTG TCT GC	AY495672	[52]
<i>ppara</i>	TCT CTT CAG CCC ACC ATC CC ATC CCA GCG TGT CGT CTC C	AY590299	[52]
<i>elovl6</i>	GTG CTG CTC TAC TCC TGG TA ACG GCA TGG ACC AAG TAG T	JX975702	[52]
<i>fads2</i>	CGA GAG CCA CAG CAG CAG GGA CGG CCT GCG CCT GAG CAG TT	GQ162822	**
<i>cox2</i>	GAG TAC TGG AAG CCG AGC AC GAT ATC ACT GCC GCC TGA GT	AM296029	[53]
<i>cpt1b</i>	CCA CCA GCC AGA CTC CAC AG CAC CAC CAG CAC CCA CAT ATT TAG	DQ866821	[54]
<i>actb</i>	TCT GTC TGG ATC GGA GGC TC AAG CAT TTG CCG TGG ACG	KY388508	[55]

* Complete gene names; *lpl*: lipoprotein lipase, *ppara*: peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha, *elovl6*: elongation of very long chain fatty acids protein 6, *fads2*: fatty acyl desaturase 2, *cox2*: cyclooxygenase-2, *cpt1*: carnitina palmitoiltransferase I, *β -act*: beta-actin. ** Submitted without separate published article.